

A Note on the Origin and Fate of Consciousness

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Abstract

In this note, we propose that knowledge of the total environment - the cosmos itself - may be included in the inputs to the theatre of individual consciousness. Informed by this mode of input, consciousness takes what we call 'total' decisions and performs 'total' actions, which are cognizant of the whole universe and its requirements. We propose certain calculations related to the consequences of the existence of this mode, which may shed light on the origin and fate of consciousness.

In [1] gravity bits were introduced as those bits which indicate the state of an axon tract in response to an impinging gravitational wave. In [2], the author studied the impact of gravitational waves on quantum information processing by a tract of axons. Thus gravity qubits can also be considered alongside gravity classical bits.

In [3], Baars proposes a multipartite model of the theatre of consciousness, its inputs and zones of processing. We ask the question: what happens to the Baars model of the theatre of consciousness if gravity bits and gravity qubits are included in it. These bits and qubits have the feature that they represent not only novel information but also correlative information between the modalities. This latter property arises because their source can couple multiple tracts and brain regions at the same time. Once coupled, these regions generate similar gravitational signatures in their signals, thereby modulating overall brain activity.

Again due to their long wavelength, gravitational waves can also couple multiple brains in multiple organisms at the same time. When certain asterisms are ascendant, as opposed to other ones, and there are gravitational events located in them, entire populations on the Earth and nearby regions of the Milky Way can be identically impacted. These bits, acting in the theatre of an individual being's consciousness thereby serve an informative role. Through close coupling, the being gets a 'sense' of those around itself - what the trends are and general perceptions are. In this way, coalitions of beings are formed and man, for example, becomes a gregarious or social animal. Entire ecosystems of thinking beings often live, act and evolve harmoniously for periods of geological time, due in part to such mutual coupling. Whereas the theory of evolution [4] studies how differences arise over time, it overlooks the overwhelming similarities

that are present. These may be understood to arise in part from long-range coupling, such as that discussed above.

An open question, also introduced in [1], is to study the impact of these bits on the theatre of consciousness, determine how the theatre evolves in their presence, compare the evolved form with the present status of consciousness in living beings, and therefrom deduce a temporal lower bound on the evolution of conscious entities in the universe. One might also be able to extend this study to determine the opposite bound and the fate or destiny of conscious entities. This would be along the lines of the concept of a ‘heat death’ of the universe [5].

References

- [1] Aman Chawla, Salvatore D. Morgera, and Arthur D. Snider. Fields, geometry, and their impact on axon interaction. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 9(4):751–778, 2021.
- [2] Aman Chawla. A gedanken experiment on the brain as a quantum computer. *ResearchGate Preprint*, 2022.
- [3] Bernard J Baars. Global workspace theory of consciousness: toward a cognitive neuroscience of human experience. *Progress in brain research*, 150:45–53, 2005.
- [4] Charles Darwin. *On the origin of species: A facsimile of the first edition*. Harvard University Press, 1964.
- [5] Pamela Zoline. The heat death of the universe. *New Worlds*, 173:148–159, 1967.